

Paganism in the 4th Century Nicomedia

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Nicomedia's aspect and well-being can be compared to an ideal city model in some ways. Originally, the city was built around Greek and Roman idols. Dionysus and Hercules were credited with building the city, and Zeus was tasked with protecting it. As time went on, the idolatry continued. A pagan Nicomedia can be seen, for example, in the second century AD. In Nicomedia, the pagan element was generally accepted, but it did not bring universal harmony. During the same period (2nd century), the first Christians began to appear in Bithynia. Christianity was seen as blasphemous to the Roman Empire and society at the time, as well as a presence associated with witchcraft; such practices threatened the rule of the Roman Empire. Nevertheless, the presence of the pagans was still bold. Nicomedia had still impressive temples and statues dedicated to the ancient gods and sacrificial altars. Nicomedia experienced a transitional period in regard to social worship in the fourth century: the beginning of the rise of Christianity and the downfall of paganism.

Date Range: 300 CE - 400 CE

Region: Eastern Roman Empire (300-600)

Region tags: Southeastern Europe, Middle East, Syria, Asia Minor, Eastern Mediterranean, Thrace, Levant, Greece, Egypt

Late Roman - Early Byzantine Empire (300-600)

Status of Participants:

- Elite
- Religious Specialists
- Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Eusebius, [Caesariensis]. Eusebius Kirchengeschichte. Edited by Eduard Schwartz. De Gruyter, 1955. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783112486825>.
- Source 2: LIBANIUS Selected Works I, Loeb Classical Library 451
- Source 3: Socrates of Constantinople, Church History

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKEwju9pfTio7_AhXjc_EDHUITat4QFnoECBEQAQ&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.dc0373%2C_Athanasius%2C_Orationes_contra_Arianos_%5BSchaff%5D%2C_EN.pdf&usg=AOvVaw2cRT6mw6Z5yppFB3BnBjaU

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

— Yes

Type of excavation:
— Scientific

Years of excavation:
— Year range: 2016-2023

Name of excavation
— Official or descriptive name: Archaeological Excavations at Nicomedia,Turkey

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Tree, grove, or forest
- Water source

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:
Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.
– Field doesn't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:
– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:
– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:
– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:
– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:
– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:
Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.
– Field doesn't know

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: The birth of Nicomedia was attributed to Zeus, Dionysius and Hercules

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Zeus, Dionysius and Hercules

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– No
Notes: It is the face of Hercules.

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– Yes

- ↳ Specify
 - King or emperor
 - Notes: Emperor Diocletian (3rd Century AD).

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

- ↳ Groups:
 - Priests
 - Slaves
 - Indentured servants
 - Captured enemies
 - Men

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Need of a new roman capital.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

- ↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
 - Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Height of average monument, meters:
 - Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

- ↳ Earth
 - Yes

- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No

- ↳ Sand
 - No

- ↳ Clay
 - Yes

- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No

- ↳ Plaster
 - No

- ↳ Wood
 - No

- ↳ Grass
 - No

- ↳ Stone
 - Yes

- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: No other material.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Field doesn't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife
– Field doesn't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
– Yes

↳ Humans
– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human narratives
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: Religious (Christian and Pagan figures).

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– No

↳ Are they other:
– Other [specify]: Greek Gods and Jesus Christ.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:
– Yes

- ↳ Is the cult statue hidden:
 - No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

- No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

- Yes

- ↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
 - Yes

- ↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Jesus Christ.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

- Yes

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: Field doesn't know.

- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Field doesn't know.

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - No

- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

- Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

- Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

- Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does this place lease out tools:
 - Field doesn't know

Public Works

- Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
- Yes

- ↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
 - Yes
- ↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
 - Yes
- ↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
 - Yes
- ↳ Function for water management:
 - Yes
- ↳ Part of the transportation network:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: No.

Writing/Scriptures

- Is non-religious writing stored at this place:
- Economic documents, records etc.
- Yes

- Are there scriptures associated with this place:
- Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

- Reference: Paganism in the 4th Century Nicomedia, Brown, Peter. *The Making of Late Antiquity*. London: Harvard University Press, 1993.
- Reference: Paganism in the 4th Century Nicomedia, David, Timothy Barnes. *Constantine and Eusebius*. Cambridge Mass.: Harvard University Press, 1984.
- Reference: Paganism in the 4th Century Nicomedia, Eusebius, [Caesariensis]. *Eusebius Kirchengeschichte*. Edited by Eduard Schwartz. De Gruyter, 1955. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783112486825>.
- Reference: Paganism in the 4th Century Nicomedia, Libanius. *Libanii Opera*. Vols. 10-11. Edited by R. Foerster. Leipzig: Teubner, 2004.
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